

NUMERICAL AND EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATIONS OF THIN-WALLED NEUTRALLY STABLE DEPLOYABLE COMPOSITE BOOMS

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ABSTRACT

This study deals with a method to realize a neutrally stable composite boom, which can be started and stopped at any point of deployment. An analytical method has been developed to assess the strain energy of an anti-symmetric angle-ply boom in coiled configuration basing on the classic laminate theory. The strain energy under different ply-angle, coiled curvatures, fiber volume fraction and matrix modulus were investigated. For the anti-symmetric angle-ply boom, there was the minimum strain energy when the ply-angle was 45°. The strain energy was a quadric function of the coiled curvatures. Besides, the strain energy is proportional to the matrix modulus and inversely proportional to fiber volume fraction. Then, a numerical procedure has been built to insight the changes of strain field during coiling process. The strain energy results from simulation and analytical model agree well with each other. Finally, a boom was manufactured which can state in several deployment cases stably.

1 INTRODUCTION

Thin-walled deployable boom can be rolled up like a carpenter tape, and are able to deploy by releasing the stored strain energy or other actuation. This character makes the thin-walled deployable boom be attractive for deployable structures. A non-bistable boom is stable only in its deployed configuration, then constraint instrument was needed to store the coiled boom. To avoid the complicated constraint mechanisms, a bi-stable boom was invented by Daton-Lovett^[1]. The bi-stable boom can be made from materials which exhibit a high apparent Poisson's ratio and stiffness, or through certain pre-stress^[2]. The fiber-reinforced composites provide a simple way to fabricate the bistable boom. The mechanism of a composite deployable boom had been studied by Iqbal^[3] and Guest^[4], the two stable states were thought as that cases where the strain energy was minimum in the local zone. The coiled state usually has higher strain energy than the extended state, thus the boom will always has the trend to the deploy state. An interesting case is that if the strain energies of both the coiled and the extended state are nearly equal to zero, will the boom stay at any position stably?

Murphey^[5] proposed a method to realize the neutral stability of a tape spring at first. Two laminas were firstly cured with designed curvatures through wrapped on spool, and then bonded together in a flat configuration. The open directions of the two laminas were towards with each other. Due to the pre-stress can't be handled quantitatively and the bonding procedure was not reliable, the produced boom exhibit noticeable imbalances. Since the pre-stress was difficult to control, a refined method was presented by Schultz^[6]. Both the bending moment parallel to the cylindrical axis of rotation and the circumferential direction in the extended configuration will vanish if the effective in-plane Poisson's ratio approaches 1 according to classical lamination theory. Three kinds of matrixes with different modulus were used to fabricate the $[45]_f$ laminates and results indicated that the soft-resin boom

showed neutrally stable. Besides, through sticking a local heating of thermoplastic layers on the boom, a hybrid boom was proposed by Guinot^[7].

With an aim of a better understanding of the mechanisms of neutrally stable boom, a model was built to assess the relationship of the strain energy and the ply-angle of an anti-symmetric angle ply laminates, coiled configuration, fiber volume fraction and matrix modulus quantitatively. Then a numerical method was provided and the coiling process was simulated. A 1 m long deployable boom was fabricated, and coiling and uncoiling process was conducted finally.

2 MECHANISMS OF NEUTRALLY STABLE DEPLOYABLE BOOMS

As to a deployable boom under cylindrical bending, if the strain energy of the coiled configuration was near zero, then the deployable boom can be started and stopped at any point of deployment without an inclination to spring out or coil.

Assuming anti-symmetric laminates for these deployable booms, the bending and stretching behavior will be coupled while the bending and twisting behavior can be decoupled according to classical lamination theory. Besides, it will be assumed that the boom is formed initially stress free in the extended configuration. The boom is straight and has uniform cross-section with a radius of curvature of R in the transverse and subtends an angle α , shown in Fig. 1.

Figure 1: The coordinate system of a typical thin-walled deployable boom

Taking the x and y axes to coincide with the longitudinal and transverse directions of the boom, as shown in Fig. 1. For an anti-symmetric angle-ply laminate $[+\theta / -\theta / +\theta / -\theta]$, the coupling between bending and twisting vanished, and the bending stiffness matrix can be obtained as^[8]:

$$D = \begin{bmatrix} D_{11} & D_{12} & 0 \\ D_{12} & D_{22} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & D_{66} \end{bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

where,

$$D_{ij} = \frac{1}{3} \sum_{k=1}^N (\bar{Q}_{ij})_k (z_k^3 - z_{k-1}^3) \quad (2)$$

in which,

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{Q}_{11} &= Q_{11} \cos^4 \theta + 2(Q_{12} + 2Q_{66}) \sin^2 \theta \cos^2 \theta + Q_{22} \sin^4 \theta \\ \bar{Q}_{12} &= (Q_{11} + Q_{22} - 4Q_{66}) \sin^2 \theta \cos^2 \theta + Q_{12} (\sin^4 \theta + \cos^4 \theta) \\ \bar{Q}_{22} &= Q_{11} \sin^4 \theta + 2(Q_{12} + 2Q_{66}) \sin^2 \theta \cos^2 \theta + Q_{22} \cos^4 \theta \\ \bar{Q}_{66} &= (Q_{11} + Q_{22} - 2Q_{12} - 2Q_{66}) \sin^2 \theta \cos^2 \theta + Q_{66} (\sin^4 \theta + \cos^4 \theta) \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

where, the bar over the \bar{Q}_{ij} denotes that we are dealing with the transformed reduced stiffnesses instead of reduced stiffnesses^[8].

In terms of the engineering constants, the reduced stiffnesses can be obtained as:

$$\left. \begin{aligned} Q_{11} &= \frac{E_1}{1 - \nu_{12}\nu_{21}} \\ Q_{12} &= \frac{\nu_{12}E_2}{1 - \nu_{12}\nu_{21}} = \frac{\nu_{21}E_1}{1 - \nu_{12}\nu_{21}} \\ Q_{22} &= \frac{E_2}{1 - \nu_{12}\nu_{21}} \\ Q_{66} &= G_{12} \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (4)$$

Note that there are four independent material properties, E_1 , E_2 , ν_{12} and G_{12} , known as apparent properties. These properties can be determined through the mechanics of materials approach shown as^[8]:

$$\left. \begin{aligned} E_1 &= E_f\nu_f + E_m(1 - \nu_f) \\ E_2 &= \frac{E_f E_m}{E_f(1 - \nu_f) + E_m\nu_f} \\ \nu_{12} &= \nu_f\nu_f + \nu_m(1 - \nu_f) \\ G_{12} &= \frac{G_f G_m}{G_f(1 - \nu_f) + G_m\nu_f} \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (5)$$

Where, E_f , ν_f , and G_f are elastic materials properties of the reinforced fiber, E_m , ν_m , and G_m are elastic materials properties of the matrix, and ν_f is the volume fraction of fiber. The matrix is isotropic materials, then $G_m = E_m / (1 + 2\nu_m)$.

Generally, the boom in any configurations has both bending and stretching strain energy. As to an anti-symmetric laminate, there is no twist behavior in the coiled configuration, and the strain energy due to tension is negligible, then only bending energy is involved. The strain energy per unit length of a coiled boom is^[3]:

$$U = \frac{\alpha R}{2} \left[D_{11}k_x^2 - 2D_{12}k_x\left(\frac{1}{R}\right) + D_{22}\left(\frac{1}{R}\right)^2 \right] \quad (6)$$

It can be easily seen that the strain energy is in proportion to the subtended angle α . Note that the longitudinal curvature of the coiled configuration is in the same sense as the transverse curvature of the extended configuration, i.e. both the center of curvature are on the same side of the boom.

Using (1)-(6), we can obtain

$$U = U(\alpha, R, \theta, t, E_f, \nu_f, G_f, E_m, \nu_m, \nu_f, k_x) \quad (7)$$

Where t is the thickness of each ply. The strain energy can be minimized by finding the appropriate combinations of the variable set $\alpha, R, \theta, t, E_f, \nu_f, G_f, E_m, \nu_m, \nu_f, k_x$.

We note that, the values of strain energy U under different ply angle θ and volume fraction of fiber ν_f are mainly considered.

3 NUMERICAL METHOD

To verify the strain energy predicted by the analytical model, a numerical method was used to simulate the coiling process of the boom. A finite element model was built through Abaqus software. The coiling process of a 0.14 m long deployable composite boom with $[+45^\circ/-45^\circ/+45^\circ/-45^\circ]$ lay-up was simulated, with the material properties shown in Table 1, $\alpha = 220^\circ$, $R = 25\text{mm}$, t

$=0.11\text{mm}$ and $\nu_f = 67\%$. Solving the Equation (4) yields the apparent properties as: $E_1 = 155.89\text{GPa}$, $E_2 = 9.96\text{GPa}$, $\nu_{12} = 0.31$ and $G_{12} = 4.88\text{GPa}$.

Properties		Value
	Fiber	
E_f , Gpa		231
ν_f		0.26
G_f , Gpa		24
	Resin	
E_m , Gpa		3.39
ν_m		0.41

Table 1: Material properties of T300 and 913 resin^[9]

The mesh element type used was a four-node shell element with reduced integration (Abaqus element type S4R).The analyzed model consisted of 1551 nodes and 1472 elements with the element length of around 3mm. Two steps were set to simulate the coiling process. Firstly, edge rotations were applied to the two edges shown in Fig. 2, and the center point was restrained with six degree of freedom. Since the edge rotations applied were self-equilibrated, no stress concentration arised at this point. Secondly, when the rolled-up configuration was shaped visually, unload the edge rotations and fully unloaded configuration can be obtained at the end of step 2.

Figure 2: Model for numerical analysis

4 EXPERIMENT

The deployable boom was manufactured by four plies of T300/913 Resin on a 49-mm-diam stainless steel mandrel sprayed with polytetrafluoroethylene(PTEE) release agent. The ply-angle was $[+45^\circ / -45^\circ / +45^\circ / -45^\circ]$ from the outside to inside of the boom. The impregnated fabric was wrapped by polypropylene(PP) tape tightly to provide consolidation pressure. Then the part was cured for 2.5h at 120°C . After cooling, the mandrel was pulled out of the tube. An oscillator was used to cut the tube into the designed shape. Finally the edges were glued with tape to minimize crack propagation. The coiled configuration was shown in Fig. 3.

Figure 3: The coiled configuration of the 1m boom

5 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Both the numerical and experimental results of the coiling process were presented in this section. The strain energy obtained through analytical model and numerical method were compared in different cases.

5.1 Coiling process simulation

A complete simulation of the coiling process of the boom was shown in Fig. 4.

Figure 4: Simulation of coiling process

As can be seen in Figure 4, the boom was initially strain-less, shown as (a). As the edge rotations increase, the configuration was nearly flat, shown as (b). Then the boom became unstable and snap begun, shown as (c). Figure (d) showed that the boom begun to roll up. In the end of the step 1, the rolled-up configuration was shaped visually, shown as (e). Finally, the edge rotation was deleted, and the fully unloaded configuration was shown as (f).

The radius of the coiled configuration was calculated through three different points in a same plane perpendicular to the coiled axis, and the numerical result was 32.70mm.

The numerical results of the coiling process can gain a detailed insight into the local deformation of the boom, from which the strain energy of the boom can be obtained and the mechanics of neutrally stable can be understood. The dynamic simulation procedures will be given in the future.

5.2 Comparison with numerical results

For a boom made by T300/913 resin unidirectional prepreg (The mechanical properties are listed in table 1), with $\alpha = 220^\circ$, $R = 25\text{mm}$, $t = 0.11\text{mm}$, the values of strain energy U for varying θ , k_x , ν_f and E_m are shown in Fig. 5 and Fig. 7 separately.

Figure 5: Strain energy with ply-angle under different coiled curvatures

Note that the fiber volume fraction is $v_f = 67\%$, and the matrix modulus is $E_m = 3.39\text{GPa}$ in Fig. 5. As can be seen in Fig. 5, there was minimum strain energy at 45° for three different coiled curvatures. The strain energy is proportional to the curvatures when the ply-angle smaller than 45° . While, there will be the minimum strain energy when $k_x = D_{12} / (D_{11} * R)$ from Equation (6). The minimum strain energy was 9.56J in the case of $\theta = 45^\circ$. The increment of the strain energy was nearly the same with curvature's increment. In contrast, the strain energies were nearly the same when the ply-angle bigger than 45° for different coiled curvatures. This partly because the bending stiffness D_{11} decreased, while the D_{22} increased when the ply-angle bigger than 45° shown in Fig. 6. Then, the changes of coiled curvatures nearly can't induce any changes of the strain energy.

Figure 6: Bending stiffness with ply-angle

Figure 7: Strain energy with ply-angle under different fiber volume fraction and matrix modulus

Note that the coiled curvature is $k_x = 1/R$ in Fig. 7. The strain energy profile is symmetric, and the minimum value exist at $\theta = 45^\circ$. The higher fiber volume fraction will produce the bigger strain energy at any ply-angle. Note that the minimum strain energy is proportional to the matrix modulus E_m , that is soft-matrix encourages neutral stability. The results were in agreement with Schultz^[6].

The strain energy in different cases calculated through analytical model and numerical method were shown in Table 2. It can be seen that the results from the analytical model correlate fairly well with the numerical results. The numerical results always smaller than the analytical results except the matrix modulus was the minimum.

Case	Analytical model, J	Finite element, J	Deviation
$E_m=0.30\text{GPa}$, $v_f=67\%$	1.06	1.12	-5.66%
$E_m=1.00\text{GPa}$, $v_f=67\%$	3.34	3.27	2.10%
$E_m=3.39\text{GPa}$, $v_f=60\%$	8.21	7.79	5.12%
$E_m=3.39\text{GPa}$, $v_f=67\%$	9.56	9.05	5.33%
$E_m=3.39\text{GPa}$, $v_f=80\%$	13.67	12.88	5.78%

Table 2: Strain energy in different cases

For $[+\theta / -\theta / +\theta / -\theta]$ lay-up boom, results indicate that 45° ply-angle can realize the minimum strain energy. Besides, the smaller coiled radius of curvature, lower fiber volume fraction and matrix modulus can decrease the strain energy.

5.3 Comparison with experimental results

The different deployment states were shown in Fig. 8.

Figure 8: Configurations of different states during deployment

The radius of the coiled configuration was 28mm, and around 12% bigger than the extended radius. Besides, the tested radius was about 16.78% smaller than the numerical result.

Note that after the boom was manufactured, once in partially deployment state freely, the boom always had the trend to the extended state. It should be noted that the boom was stable both in coiled and extended state. About one week later, the deployable process was demonstrated again. It can be found that the boom can keep static in several partially deployable phases. We thought that the pre-stress contribute to these phenomena. During the curing process, the prepregs were tensioned, then the pre-stress was introduced. The effect of pre-stress should be investigated in the future fabricated procedures.

Since the matrix modulus used was 3.39GPa, the strain energy in the coiled was still a little higher. More soft resin will be tested in the future.

6 CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, the bending strain energy equation of a deployable composite boom in coiled configuration considering both the geometry and material parameters quantitatively was proposed. For an anti-symmetric angle-ply boom, the strain energy values under different ply-angle, coiled radius, fiber volume fraction and matrix modulus were calculated. Then, a numerical method was built to investigate the strain field during different deployment states. The coiled strain energy obtained through analytical model and numerical method correlated well with each other. Finally, a 1 m deployable boom was fabricated, and the coiling and extending process were tested. A refined analytical model considered nonlinear behavior and related manufactured procedures are in study to realize neutrally stable boom.

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